

“ULLI-KHOVLI” CULTURAL COMPLEX

Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnudbek ugli

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13999651>

The Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have lived with common goals as close friends, close neighbors, and strategic partners since time immemorial. Therefore, the roots of the relations between the two countries go back to a long history and are built on the basis of mutual respect and trust.

Today, it is important to talk about the relations of friendship with Turkmenistan, one of the close partners of Uzbekistan, which are being implemented and which are rising to a new level. After all, historical work has been carried out to raise relations between the two friendly countries in the social, economic, cultural and educational spheres to a new level, and to develop mutually beneficial cooperation, defining new directions and perspectives of cooperation.

At this point, it is worth saying that among the representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in Uzbekistan today, more than 206 thousand Turkmen brothers are working for the development of our beloved country. Today, in order to preserve and develop the national culture, language, traditions and customs of the Turkmen in our country, all opportunities and conditions have been created for the activity of the Republican Turkmen cultural center.

In order to promote the harmonious ethnographic culture of the Uzbek-Turkmen peoples who have lived in the same space based on common goals, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2020 "Uzbek-Turkmen friendship house in Khorezm region" and on the basis of the decision on measures to establish the directorate of the "Ulli Khovli" (meaning "big yard") complex, "Uzbek- Many efforts have been made to preserve the buildings and structures located in the "Turkman Friendship House" and "Ulli Khovli" complex, and to pass them on to the next generation.

The "Ulli Khovli" complex, reconstructed in order to further strengthen the close neighborly relations between the two countries, is one of the historical monuments in the Khorezm oasis. In the architectural monument built in the 17th century, ancient courtyards, relics of Turkmen culture, and the fortress walls surrounding them have been preserved.

Currently, a twenty-bed hotel, a museum, a cinema hall, a photo gallery, special places for breeding the famous Akhaltaka horses, nortuyas have been established in the complex, and national monuments of the Turkmen people

have been established. As a result, "Ulli Khovli" has become a tourist center, attracting more and more travelers who want to visit the authentic atmosphere of the 17th century, and the guests of the renovated "Ulli Khovli" complex can ride horses, see how flour is made in the mill, taste various national dishes. All conditions were created for them to taste.

The "Ulli Khovli" complex is always open to anyone who wants to travel to the past of the ancient walled fortress and learn about the roots of the cultures and friendly relations between the two peoples. All conditions for tourism have been created in the territory of the complex. Several expositions - old photographs, workshops of artisans, mini-hotel with 20 beds were built. National games, wrestling competitions, performances of artists, folklore performances, cooking lessons from Uzbek and Turkmen national dishes are held.

Also, cultural and educational relations between our brotherly nations are becoming more active every year, various concerts and festivals, exhibitions are organized, cultural and film days are held, Turkmen national cultural centers are working in our country.

It should be said that the history, culture and traditions that connect the Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have become the common property of our peoples. This closeness serves as a solid basis for the development of cultural and humanitarian ties.

Another important point. In our country, all conditions have been created for the preservation and development of the Turkmen language, culture, and traditions. In particular, there are 44 schools that teach in the Turkmen language in Uzbekistan. Turkmen philology of Karakalpak State University, Turkmen language teachers are being trained at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajinyoz. This is also an example of the high attention paid to the common culture and history of the two brotherly peoples.

References:

1. Ismailov, T. (2022, November). THE FORT THAT SPEAKS FROM THE PAST. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 18-22).
2. Ismailov, T. (2024). PALACE OF THE KHOREZMSHAKH. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(3), 5-7.
3. Ismailov, T. (2024). KO'HNA VA HAMISHA NAVQIRON SHAHAR. *Молодые ученые*, 2(2), 71-72.
4. Ismailov, T. (2023). EMBOSSED KHIVA PILLARS. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(4), 63-66.

5. Ismailov, T. (2024). MONUMENTS OF ANCIENT KHOREZM. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(4), 175-176.
6. Ismailov, T. (2024). SULTON UVAYS ZIYORATGOHI. Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 3(4), 46-47.
7. Ismailov, T. (2024). QADIMGI XORAZM YODGORLIKLARI-TUPROQQAL'A. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 3(4), 104-105.
8. Ismailov, T. (2024). THE LIGHT FROM THE SHOVIOT. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 9-13.
9. Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2023). Hazrati Pahlavon Mahmud maqbarasi. Science and Education, 4(3), 106-113.

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES

